

Role of chloride in the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T

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Kinetics of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid over a wide range. The rate- $[H^+]$ plots show nearly bell-shaped profiles in the presence of added chloride. The rate-dependence in $[CAT]$ changes from second order to first order as $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ are varied. The reactions generally show fractional order kinetics in $[AA]$ and inverse dependence in $[H^+]$ except in the acid range $0.05-0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Mechanisms consistent with the observed results are discussed. The rate-limiting steps have been identified and constants of these steps calculated. Activation parameters corresponding to these steps have also been computed. Validity of Taft equation has been tested. The study establishes the significant role of chloride in chloramine-T oxidations in acid medium. The chloride effect is more pronounced at high acid concentrations.

Mechanism of oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is of considerable interest¹⁻⁴. It is one of the important biochemical processes and hence a potential area for intensive investigation. Although some work on the effect of chloride on the kinetics of oxidation of some amino acids by chloramine-T has been reported, there are some inconsistencies and the work is incomplete². The effect as function of $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ has not been systematically investigated. Hence it was thought worthwhile to complete the work aimed at deducing a comprehensive mechanism for the oxidation of amino acids in the presence of chloride and to establish the role of chloride in positive chlorine oxidations.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data on the oxidations of alanine (Ala), valine (Val), leucine (Leu), serine (Ser), glutamine (Gln) and glutamic acid (Glu) by chloramine-T (CAT) as functions of $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ are shown in Tables 1-6 and Figs. 1-4. The rates- $[H^+]$ plots showed nearly bell-shaped profiles even in the presence of added chloride (Fig. 1). The rate dependence in $[CAT]$ was changed from second order to first order as $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ were varied. The kinetics were therefore determined as functions of $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$. The rates were also measured at different temperatures as functions of $[AA]$ and the corresponding activation parameters computed as described under discussion. The kinetics at very low $[H^+]$ ($<0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were complicated and the rate showed second order kinetics in $[CAT]$, fractional order in $[AA]$ and inverse dependence in $[H^+]$.

As the $[H^+]$ was increased beyond 0.05 mol dm^{-3} , the rate dependence in $[CAT]$ was changed from second order to first order. This condition was a function of $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$. At low $[Cl^-]$, the change of order was observed at a

Fig. 1. (i) Plots of k_{obs} vs $[HClO_4]$ and (ii) plots of k'_{obs} vs $[HClO_4]$, temp 303 K. $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 50 [AA]_0 = 20 [Cl^-] = 3.33 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

relatively high $[H^+]$, while at high $[Cl^-]$ this condition was achieved even at a lower $[H^+]$ (Table 6). The change of rate-dependence may be due to the change in reactive form of the oxidant. The rates showed positive dependence in $[H^+]$ in the narrow range of $0.05-0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate exhibited slight dependence in $[AA]$. The reactions beyond

Table 1. Pseudo-first and second order rate constants for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids (AA) by chloramine-T (CAT) in the presence of chloride as $[\text{HClO}_2]$ varied at 303 K*

$[\text{HClO}_2]$ 10^2 mol dm^{-3}	Ala		Val		Leu		Ser		Gln		Glu	
	1.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	5.0
	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)	(1)	(2)
0.05	5.6	9.7	4.5	8.3	7.4	8.3	10.4	8.3	8.5	8.8	26.4	26.4
0.1	16.3	16.5	6.9	12.9	10.7	16.7	20.5	16.2	20.2	12.6	26.4	26.4
0.2	40.4	60	93.9	18.1	53.3	44.4	63.6	20.8	38.1	69.2	60.0	61.1
0.3	-	60	-	26.6	-	36.7	46.3	-	51.7	-	76.6	73.3
0.5	33.3	60	133.3	25.6	40.0	42.9	74.1	25.6	56.4	90.9	61.1	69.1
1.0	23.3	75.9	133.3	19.9	60.1	34.1	74.1	13.9	52.9	71.8	33.3	46.3
2.0	13.6	39.7	111.1	11.5	67.6	11.6	48.7	7.1	26.9	48.9	13.9	30.5
3.0	11.0	28.4	70.4	6.3	43.9	6.4	41.9	4.7	17.9	40.7	8.9	9.9
5.0	6.9	11.1	44.0	3.0	20.2	3.5	29.2	2.9	10.3	30.9	4.6	3.8
10.0	1.9	6.4	15.9	2.2	7.7	4.9	23.0	1.85	5.1	11.7	6.8	6.6
20.0	2.7	6.5	10.9	2.8	8.5	6.8	18.6	2.5	5.2	7.7	8.6	9.4
30.0	3.2	5.4	7.0	3.1	7.3	11.3	14.7	2.8	3.0	6.2	5.3	7.1
50.0	2.9	4.3	5.4	3.3	5.0	7.0	9.4	2.6	3.0	5.1	2.7	5.6
100.0	2.2	2.8	3.0	2.3	3.5	4.6	5.8	1.8	1.9	3.5	1.3	3.9

At $10^2 [\text{Cl}^-] (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$, (1) $10^4 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$; (2) $10 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$

$10^2 [\text{CAT}]_0 = 50 [\text{AA}]_0 = 3.33, I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Fig 2 Plots of k_{obs} vs [AA], (A) $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 3.33$, $[HClO_4] = 3.33$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [Cl^-] (\text{mol dm}^{-3}) = 1.0$ (i) 5.0 (ii) and (B) $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 2$, $[HClO_4] = 3.33$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^2 [Cl^-] (\text{mol dm}^{-3}) = 5.0$ (i) 20.0 (ii)

Fig 3 (i) Plots of k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ and (ii) plots of k_{obs} vs $[Cl^-]$ (i) $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 5.0$, $[AA] = 2.0$, $[Cl^-] = 1.0 (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$ and (ii) $10^3 [CAT]_0 = 5.0$, $[AA] = 1.0 (\text{mol dm}^{-3})$, $10^2 [HClO_4] (\text{mol dm}^{-3}) = 5.0$ (A) 50.0 (B)

Fig 4 Plots of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$

$[HClO_4] > 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ also showed first order kinetics in $[CAT]$, but exhibited higher fractional order in $[AA]$ and inverse fractional dependence in $[H^+]$. The reactions under these conditions may go through competitive pathways 4 and 5 in Scheme 1

Mechanisms of oxidation The observed kinetics for the oxidation of amino acids in the presence of chloride in the entire acid range may be explained by the comprehensive mechanism shown in Scheme 1

Path 1

Path 2

Path 3

Path 4

Path 5

Path 6

Scheme 1

The combined rate law for pathways 1-3 has been deduced,

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\frac{d[CAT]}{dt} &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [CAT]^2 [SH^+]}{[H^+] + K_1 K_2 [SH^+]} + \frac{K_4^2 k_5 [CAT]^2 [H_2O]^2}{[H^+]^2} \\
 &+ \frac{K_6 k_7 [CAT] [Cl^-]}{1 + K_6 [Cl^-]} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 2. Pseudo-second order rate constants for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride at low [HClO₄] as [Cl⁻] varied at 303 K*

10 ² [Cl ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 k _{obs} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)					
	Ala	Val	Leu	Ser	Gln	Glu
1.0	13.6	6.3	9.5	10.7	7.8	11.9
2.0	20.8	-	10.1	14.5	9.3	19.7
3.0	27.2	-	10.4	20.9	10.5	25.6
5.0	39.7	43.9	11.6	26.9	14.0	30.6
10.0	57.3	-	12.9	44.4	22.0	46.4
20.0	111.1	85.7	48.7	54.8	38.0	-

*10³ [CAT]₀ = 50 [AA]₀ = 33.3 [HClO₄] = 3.33, I = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

$$\text{If we take } -\frac{1}{[\text{CAT}]^2} \frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} \approx d \frac{\{1/[\text{CAT}]\}}{dt} \approx k_{\text{obs}}$$

then the rate law (1) takes the form,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SH}^+]} + \frac{K_4^2 k_5 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{K_6 k_7 [\text{Cl}^-]}{\{1 + K_6 [\text{Cl}^-]\} [\text{CAT}]} \quad (2)$$

At low [H⁺], if K₁, K₂ and K₆ are smaller, then the rate law (2) becomes

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_4^2 k_5 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{K_6 k_7 [\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CAT}]} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = K_2 k_3 [\text{S}] + \frac{K_4^2 k_5 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{K_6 k_7 [\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CAT}]}, \text{ as } [\text{S}] = \frac{K_1 [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or } k_{\text{obs}} = k[\text{S}] + \frac{k'}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k''[\text{Cl}^-]}{[\text{CAT}]} \quad (5)$$

where, $k = K_2 k_3$, $k' = K_4^2 k_5 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]^2$ and $k'' = K_6 k_7$

The plots of k_{obs} vs [AA] (Fig. 2) and k_{obs} vs [Cl⁻] (Fig. 3) are linear in accordance with the rate law (5). Slight decrease of the pseudo-second order rate constants, in this acid range, with increase in [CAT] is also in conformity with the rate law. The values of k for all the amino acids at different temperatures were calculated from the plots of

Table 3. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride at high [HClO₄] as [Cl⁻] varied at 303 K*

10 ² [Cl ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k'_{\text{obs}} (s ⁻¹) at 10 [HClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)											
	Ala		Val		Leu		Ser		Gln		Glu	
2.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	2.0	5.0	
1.0	3.2	2.9	2.8	3.1	3.4	5.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	2.1	3.4	4.6
2.0	5.0	4.2	-	3.5	6.6	6.3	3.8	2.9	5.3	2.3	5.3	4.9
3.0	6.0	4.5	-	4.1	9.0	7.0	4.6	3.0	6.8	2.4	7.1	5.3
5.0	7.3	4.7	8.5	4.2	11.3	7.1	5.2	3.1	9.0	2.7	9.2	5.6
10.0	9.1	5.0	-	5.1	16.6	7.7	6.0	3.4	11.3	3.0	12.8	6.1
20.0	10.9	5.4	11.9	5.2	18.6	9.4	7.7	4.8	-	-	-	-

*[CAT]₀ = 50[AA]₀ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

Table 4. Pseudo-second order rate constants (k_{obs}) for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride in aqueous medium at low [HClO₄] = 0.03 mol dm⁻³

10 ³ [CAT] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [AA] ₀ mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹) at 10 ² [Cl ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)											
		Ala			Val			Leu			Ser		Gln
		1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	20.0	5.0
Effect of varying [CAT] ₀ :													
0.3	2.0	12.8	41.2	69.1	11.4	45.3	85.7	7.1	11.6	35.7	3.5	82.7	17.8
0.5	2.0	12.3	40.3	68.8	-	44.8	83.4	6.8	-	38.7	4.1	58.3	15.9
1.0	2.0	11.1	40.2	70.1	11.5	43.5	85.7	6.0	11.6	41.9	4.4	40.7	14.2
2.0	2.0	10.7	40.7	70.0	9.4	42.3	87.1	5.9	9.8	42.1	3.9	32.7	12.8
3.0	2.0	10.3	40.0	72.3	8.3	40.4	90.2	5.6	9.4	42.4	3.2	21.4	12.8
Effect of varying [AA] ₀ :													
1.0	0.5	-	26.0	28.3	8.3	33.3	55.6	3.2	-	41.9	-	18.7	11.9
1.0	1.0	10.1	33.3	49.2	10.2	39.2	72.4	3.7	7.5	40.9	3.8	26.9	10.7
1.0	2.0	11.1	40.0	70.4	11.5	43.8	85.6	6.0	11.6	41.9	4.4	40.7	14.4
1.0	3.0	12.7	51.1	103.6	12.1	46.0	99.9	7.4	15.3	42.1	7.4	47.6	17.1
1.0	5.0	18.3	59.4	113.9	14.2	-	114.3	13.7	23.3	41.5	11.5	74.9	25.4

k_{obs} vs [AA] (Fig 2 and Table 7) The corresponding activation parameters for all the amino acids have also been computed (Table 7)

The reactions in the acid range 0.01–0.05 mol dm⁻³ may mostly go through steps shown in path 4 of Scheme 1. The related rate law is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = \frac{K_8 k_9 [\text{ArSO}_2\text{NHCl}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-] [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{1 + K_8 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{or } k'_{obs} = \frac{K_8 k'_9 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K_8 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}, \text{ where } k'_9 = k_9 [\text{H}_2\text{O}] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{k'_{obs}} = \frac{1}{K_8 k'_9} \frac{1}{[\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k'_9} \quad (8)$$

The plots of $1/k'_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $1/k'_{obs}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ are linear consistent with rate law (8) (Fig 3). The observed

kinetics in this acid range can be explained by the competitive pathways 5 and 6 in the comprehensive mechanism. Under these conditions, the oxidant mostly exists as $(\text{ArSO}_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl})^+$

The combined rate laws (9–11) deduced based on paths 5 and 6 (Scheme 1) account for the observed results in this acid range,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_{10} [\text{CAT}] [\text{Cl}^-] + K_1 k_{11} \frac{[\text{CAT}] [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{or } k_{obs} = k_{10} [\text{Cl}^-] + K_1 k_{11} [\text{SH}^+] / [\text{H}^+] \quad (10)$$

$$\text{or } k_{obs} = k_{10} [\text{Cl}^-] + k_{11} [\text{S}] \quad (11)$$

Two sets of constants k_{10} and k_{11} were calculated from the plots of k_{obs} vs [AA] and k_{obs} vs [Cl⁻] (Figs 2–3). Further values of k_{10} and k_{11} at different temperatures were calculated by varying [AA] at each temperature. The cor-

Table 5 Pseudo first order rate constants for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine T in the presence of chloride at high $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

[CAT] ₀ 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[AA] ₀ 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k'_{obs} (s ⁻¹) at 10 ² [Cl ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)													
		Ala			Val			Leu			Ser			Gln	Glu
		1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	5.0	5.0
Effect of varying [CAT] ₀															
0.30	2.0	2.9	3.6	5.3	3.6	3.3	5.9	5.5	8.0	9.6	2.5	4.1	4.1	2.5	7.7
0.50	2.0	2.9	3.6	5.4	3.6	3.6	5.8	5.3	6.9	9.5	2.4	3.5	4.5	2.6	6.5
1.0	2.0	2.9	3.7	5.4	3.1	3.8	5.6	5.1	7.1	9.4	2.6	3.0	4.8	2.8	5.5
2.0	2.0	2.8	3.8	5.3	3.3	3.5	5.3	5.5	6.6	9.5	-	2.9	-	2.1	5.0
3.0	2.0	2.9	3.6	5.3	3.2	3.2	4.6	5.6	6.8	9.4	2.4	2.7	4.7	2.2	5.1
Effect of varying [AA]															
1.0	0.5	2.3	1.8	3.6	2.3	2.1	3.3	3.2	4.0	4.2	1.6	2.0	2.5	1.9	2.7
1.0	1.0	2.4	2.5	4.5	2.8	2.9	4.0	4.2	4.8	6.3	2.1	2.5	3.2	2.3	3.7
1.0	2.0	2.9	3.6	5.4	3.1	3.8	5.6	5.1	7.0	9.4	2.6	3.0	4.8	2.7	5.6
1.0	3.0	3.3	4.3	6.5	3.6	4.2	6.3	5.2	9.6	11.7	3.0	3.7	5.9	3.2	7.0
1.0	5.0	3.6	6.6	8.9	4.5	5.9	7.3	6.0	12.6	16.8	3.5	4.8	7.4	3.9	-

Table 6 Kinetic data for the oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids by chloramine T in the presence of chloride at 303 K

Orders observed in	[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	At 10 ² [Cl ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)													
		Ala			Val			Leu			Ser			Gln	Glu
		1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	1.0	5.0	20.0	5.0	5.0
[CAT]	0.01–0.05	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	1–2	1–2	2.0	2.0
	0.05–0.20	-	-	1.0	-	-	1.0	-	1.0	-	-	1.0	-	1.0	1.0
	0.20–1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
[AA]	0.01–0.05	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.4	+ve	0.7	0	-	0.4	0.6	0.5	0.2
	0.05–0.20	-	-	0	-	-	0	-	0.2	-	-	0.3	-	0.3	0.3
	0.20–1.0	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.5	0.3	0.5
[H ⁺]	0.01–0.05	-0.7	-1.1	-0.95	-1.0	-1.0	-0.6	-1.2	-1.1	-0.5	-0.9	-1.0	-0.5	-1.1	-1.1
	0.05–0.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.1	0.8	-	1.1	0	-	0.5	0.5
	0.20–1.0	-0.3	-0.5	-0.7	-0.7	-0.5	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7	-0.7	-	-0.6	-0.6	-1.2	-0.5

Table 7. Values of k at different temperatures and the corresponding activation parameters

Temp K	$10^3 k$ ($\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at $10^2 [\text{Cl}^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})									
	Ala		Val		Leu		Scr	Gln	Glu	
	1.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	1.0	5.0	5.0	
293	1.2	5.4	0.63	2.3	1.1	2.0	1.1	1.7	1.1	
298	-	-	-	-	-	2.3	-	2.3	-	
303	1.4	7.5	1.3	2.3	2.3	3.3	2.1	3.3	2.1	
308	4.8	9.6	2.0	2.5	3.4	6.4	3.4	5.2	2.6	
Activation parameters calculated from ^a										
E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	74.4	30.6	57.7	58.2	46.8	46.8	47.4	46.2	43.3	
$\log A$	10.2	3.2	9.55	7.3	5.4	5.6	5.5	5.5	4.8	
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1})	70.9	29.5	66.6	17.4	54.7	-40.2	6.9	55.5	44.1	
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	-3.5	-130.9	-220.7	-180.7	-57.3	-102.2	-84.0	-51.9	-93.1	
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1})	72.0	69.1	73.5	72.2	72.1	71.2	72.4	71.2	72.3	

^aSee text and eqn (6).

responding activation parameters have also been computed (Table 8).

Applicability of Taft equation⁵ for the oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T in the presence of chloride ion has also been tested. The following typical equations are found to be valid (figure not shown),

$$\log k = -0.23 \sigma^* - 2.60 \quad (12)$$

$$\log k_{11} = -0.19 \sigma^* - 1.95 \quad (13)$$

$$\log k = -0.19 E_s - 2.70 \quad (14)$$

$$\log k_{11} = -0.42 E_s - 1.58 \quad (15)$$

The free energies of activation in the low and high $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ ranges are almost constant (Tables 7, 8) signalling operation of similar mechanisms in the respective ranges. Further, the plots of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are linear (Fig. 4).

A typical detailed mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by chloramine-T corresponding to the formation of nitriles and aldehydes as products is shown in Scheme 2¹⁻³.

Conclusions: This study establishes the significant role of chloride on the rates and mechanism of CAT oxidations. The chloride effect is more pronounced at high $[\text{H}^+]$. The rate-dependence in $[\text{CAT}]$ changes from second order to first order as the $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ are increased. This change of order in $[\text{CAT}]$ could be achieved at a lower $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.05–0.20 mol dm^{-3}), if the $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is about 0.20 mol dm^{-3} or at low $[\text{Cl}^-]$, if the $[\text{HClO}_4] > 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The changes in kinetics of oxidations are due to the changes in reactive form of the oxidant species in the presence of chloride under varying $[\text{H}^+]$.

Scheme 2

Experimental

The purity of chloramine-T (Fluka, A.G.) was checked by iodometric estimation of the amount of active chlorine present in it and its aqueous stock solution (0.05 mol dm^{-3})

Table 8 Values of $10^3 k_{10}$ and $10^3 k_{11}$ at different temperatures, and the corresponding activation parameters

Temp K	At 10^{-3} [Cl] mol/dm																									
	Ala						Val						Leu						Ser						Gln	
	10	50	100	200	500	1000	10	50	100	200	500	1000	10	50	100	200	500	1000	10	50	100	200	500	1000	10	50
	k_{10}	k_{11}	k_1	k_{11}	k_{10}	k_{11}																				
293	9.0	1.4	2.4	1.8	0.35	3.9	11.0	0.99	2.0	1.6	0.5	2.9	3.5	6.7	1.0	6.1	6.0	2.9	1.6	2.4	0.7	1.2	2.4	2.3		
303	2.0	4.5	2.8	10.0	1.3	12.3	21.0	5.0	3.6	8.0	1.3	12.5	4.0	20.4	2.0	27.0	13.0	4.8	3.4	3.2	1.6	9.2	1.6	4.3		
308	3.0	6.6	6.0	16.1	1.9	20.9	30.0	6.9	5.2	15.2	1.9	20.1	8.0	35.7	3.0	62.2	26.0	6.6	6.4	11.4	-	-	6.0	10.4		
Activation parameters calculated from*																										
E_a	82.2	64.9	43.9	117.8	85.9	83.2	85.8	49.0	49.1	97.5	65.2	65.2	43.2	84.5	56.0	56.0	43.3	70.7	74.0	76.9	64.7	64.7	94.6	82.3		
(kJ mol ⁻¹)																										
log A	12.5	8.9	5.9	18.3	11.9	12.4	13.1	6.2	6.0	14.7	8.3	9.3	5.2	12.9	6.9	8.1	5.6	9.9	10.3	10.8	8.4	9.1	13.9	11.8		
$\Delta H^\ddagger$	81.4	62.5	110.1	71.4	85.1	80.62	90.5	45.5	46.9	99.9	67.6	78.8	41.4	84.5	53.6	118.3	37.3	70.9	67.4	76.6	62.5	113.7	51.9	71.5		
(kJ mol ⁻¹)																										
$\Delta S^\ddagger$	-8.8	-83.6	85.9	-47.7	-19.6	15.4	21.6	-138.8	-136.8	44.6	-77.5	-21.4	-150.8	1.63	-120.4	185.7	-158.4	-55.6	-69.3	-39.6	-92.1	91.2	-120.2	-54.3		
(JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)																										
$\Delta G^\ddagger$	108.3	87.8	84.0	85.8	91.0	76.0	156.2	88.4	88.4	86.4	91.1	85.2	87.1	84.1	90.1	83.3	87.1	87.6	89.4	88.6	90.4	86.1	88.3	87.9		
(kJ mol ⁻¹)																										

See text and eqn (12)

was prepared, standardised and preserved in dark coloured bottles. Chromatographically pure amino acids alanine, valine, leucine, serine, glutamine and glutamic acid (Sisco) were further assayed⁶. Aqueous stock solutions of the compounds (0.10 mol dm⁻³) were used. Sodium chloride was used as a source of chloride ion. Ionic strength of the medium was kept at 0.3 mol dm⁻³ by employing concentrated aqueous solutions of sodium nitrate. All other reagents employed were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements : The kinetic runs were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo order conditions with [AA] >> [CAT] (5–50 times). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of known amounts of oxidant solution (0.0003–0.003 mol dm⁻³), pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to mixtures containing the required amounts of amino acid (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), perchloric acid (0.0005–0.10 mol dm⁻³), sodium chloride (0.01–0.20 mol dm⁻³) and water, in the boiling tube thermostated at the same temperature. Progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric determination of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-second order and pseudo-first order rate constants were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within 3% error.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometries of CAT-amino acid oxidations were determined at varying [H⁺] and [Cl⁻] by equilibrating varying ratios of [CAT] to [AA] at 303 K. The corresponding nitriles were the major products at low [H⁺] and aldehydes at high [H⁺]. The nitriles, aldehydes, CO₂ and NH₃ were identified by standard tests⁷. Toluene-*p*-sulfonamide, the reduced product of the oxidant was detected by paper chromatography with benzyl alcohol saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the

spray reagent. The observed stoichiometries may be represented by

where, R = CH₃ (Ala), (CH₃)₂CH (Val), (CH₃)₂CHCH₂ (Leu), HOH₂C (Ser), NH₂COCH₂CH₂ (Gln), HOOCCH₂CH₂ (Glu) and Ar = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄.

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